

To Study Association of Serum Gamma Glutamyl Transferase in Acute Stroke

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Abstract:

Background: A stroke is defined as a sudden onset neurological deficit lasting more than 24 hours presumed to be of focal vascular origin. According to the World Health Organization, stroke is the leading cause of death after heart disease. Studies conducted in Indian communities reveal a significant variation in stroke prevalence, ranging from 150 to 900 cases per lac.

Material & Methods: The present case control study was carried out at department of General Medicine, at our tertiary care hospital. The study duration was of six months from January 2023 to June 2023. The study included 100 participants among them 50 patients aged 40 to 80 years who were diagnosed with acute stroke, encompassing first-time occurrences of intracerebral hemorrhage, ischemic stroke, and subarachnoid haemorrhage and 50 controls.

Results: In the present study, out of total study participants, mean serum GGT levels among cases was 56.84 ± 4.9 U/L and among controls it was 16.84 ± 3.2 U/L. This difference was statistically significant (p value < 0.05). Out of the total study participants majority of cases (62%) were of Hemorrhagic stroke. Based on type of stroke, mean serum GGT levels among cases of hemorrhagic stroke was 59.5 ± 2.9 U/L and among cases of ischemic stroke it was 53.62 ± 5.2 U/L. However, this difference was statistically not significant (p value > 0.05).

Conclusion: We concluded from the present study that our study findings suggest that elevated serum gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) levels are significantly associated with an increased risk of stroke. This highlights the potential role of GGT as a biomarker for stroke risk assessment.

Keywords: GGT, Hemorrhagic stroke, Ischemic stroke.

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Introduction

A stroke is defined as a sudden onset neurological deficit lasting more than 24 hours presumed to be of focal vascular origin. [1]. According to the World Health Organization, stroke is the leading cause of death after heart disease. The Centres for Disease Control and Prevention reports that 1 in 6 cardiovascular disease deaths are due to stroke [2]. Studies conducted in Indian communities reveal a significant variation in stroke prevalence, ranging from 150 to 900 cases per lac [3].

The definitive signs of a stroke must persist for over 24 hours and can include unilateral or bilateral motor or sensory impairment, speech defects, visual field defects, conjugate deviation, acute onset apraxia or ataxia, or perceptual deficits [4]. Other signs may include changes in consciousness and reduced blood circulation to specific brain regions. Ischemic stroke occurs due to artery

occlusion, confirmed through clinical examination and neuroimaging. Hemorrhagic stroke involves bleeding within the brain tissue and is also diagnosed clinically and via neuroimaging [5].

Several risk factors contribute to the occurrence of stroke, with age, male gender, smoking, obesity, and dyslipidemia being particularly significant. One emerging factor gaining attention is gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT), traditionally recognized as an indicator of liver disease [6]. Recent research has highlighted the potential role of GGT as a biomarker for predicting stroke risk [7]. This study aims to determine whether serum GGT levels have an influence on stroke risk, specifically in individuals without a history of alcohol consumption.

Materials & Methods

The present case control study was carried out at department of General Medicine, at our tertiary care hospital. The study duration was of six months from January 2023 to June 2023. A sample size of 100 was calculated at 95% confidence interval at 10% acceptable margin of error by epi info software version 7.3. In this prospective study patients of age of both the genders were enrolled for the study. All patients who were diagnosed with acute stroke were enrolled from indoor department by simple random sampling included as cases. Institutional Ethics Committee Clearance was obtained before start of study and written and informed consent for the procedure was obtained from all the patients. Strict confidentiality was maintained with patient identity and data and not revealed, at any point of time.

In the present study, we enrolled 100 participants among them 50 patients aged 40 to 80 years who were diagnosed with acute stroke, encompassing first-time occurrences of intracerebral hemorrhage, ischemic stroke, and subarachnoid hemorrhage. The study was divided into two groups, each comprising 50 individuals. Group A consisted of participants diagnosed with acute stroke, while Group B included age and sex-matched control subjects who did not exhibit any signs of cerebrovascular or cardiovascular diseases. Individuals were excluded from the study if they had a prior history of stroke, did not have an acute stroke diagnosis, or had conditions or factors known to be associated with elevated serum gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) levels. These criteria ensured that the study focused specifically on first-time stroke events and eliminated potential confounding factors related to elevated GGT. All data were entered in the MS office

2010 spread sheet and Epi Info v7. Data analysis was carried out using SPSS v22. Qualitative data was expressed as percentage (%) and Pearson's chi square test was used to find out statistical differences between the study groups and sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value and negative predictive value were calculated. If the expected cell count was < 5 in more than 20% of the cells then Fisher's exact test was used. All tests were done at alpha (level significance) of 5%; means a significant association present if p value was less than 0.05 and highly significant if p value less than 0.01.

Results

In this study, 100 participants were enrolled, including 50 patients aged 40–80 years with first-time acute stroke (intracerebral hemorrhage, ischemic stroke, or subarachnoid hemorrhage). The participants were divided into two groups: Group A (50 stroke patients) and Group B (50 age- and sex-matched controls without cerebrovascular or cardiovascular diseases). This design allowed for a clear comparison between those affected by stroke and a healthy control group, helping to evaluate the potential role of serum gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) in stroke occurrence. The mean age of the cases was 60.2 ± 5.4 years and mean age of controls was 58.8 ± 6.9 years. Out of the total study participants majority of cases (52%) were in the age group of 60-80 years, which was followed by (28%) patients in the age group of 50-60 years and 20% cases in the age group of 40-50 years. Out of the total study participants majority of cases (58%) were male. Out of the total study participants majority of cases (62%) were of Hemorrhagic stroke. (Table 1)

Table 1: Distribution of study participants according to study parameters.

Parameters	Cases (n=50)	Controls (n=50)
Mean age	60.2 ± 5.4 years	58.8 ± 6.9 years
Age group (years)		
40-50	20%	20%
50-60	28%	32%
60-80	52%	48%
Gender		
Male	58%	52%
Female	42%	48%
Type of stroke		
Hemorrhagic stroke	62%	-
Ischemic stroke	38%	

In the present study, out of total study participants, mean serum GGT levels among cases was 56.84 ± 4.9 U/L and among controls it was 16.84 ± 3.2 U/L. This difference was statistically significant (p value < 0.05). Based on type of stroke, mean serum GGT levels among cases of hemorrhagic stroke was 59.5 ± 2.9 U/L and among cases of ischemic stroke it was 53.62 ± 5.2 U/L.

However, this difference was statistically not significant (p value > 0.05) (Table 2).

Table 2: Distribution of study participants according to Mean serum GGT levels.

Parameters	Mean serum GGT levels	P value
Cases (n=50)	56.84 ± 4.9 U/L	<0.05
Controls (n=50)	16.84 ± 3.2 U/L	
Type of stroke		
Hemorrhagic stroke	59.5 ± 2.9 U/L	> 0.05
Ischemic stroke	53.62 ± 5.2 U/L	

Discussion

In the present study, we enrolled 100 patients aged 40 to 80 years who were diagnosed with acute stroke, encompassing first-time occurrences of intracerebral hemorrhage, ischemic stroke, and subarachnoid hemorrhage. The study was divided into two groups, each comprising 50 individuals. Group A consisted of participants diagnosed with acute stroke, while Group B included age and sex-matched control subjects who did not exhibit any signs of cerebrovascular or cardiovascular diseases. This design allowed for a clear comparison between those affected by stroke and a healthy control group, helping to evaluate the potential role of serum gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) in stroke occurrence. Similar findings were reported in a study conducted by Susanta B et al among 128 patients of acute stroke over 5 years and found similar results to present study [8].

In the present study, the mean age of the cases was 60.2 ± 5.4 years and mean age of controls was 58.8 ± 6.9 years. Out of the total study participants majority of cases (52%) were in the age group of 60-80 years, which was followed by (28%) patients in the age group of 50-60 years and 20% cases in the age group of 40-50 years. Out of the total study participants majority of cases (58%) were male. Out of the total study participants majority of cases (62%) were of Hemorrhagic stroke. Similar findings were reported in a study conducted by P Jousilahti et al among patients of acute stroke and found significant association between serum GGT levels and occurrence of stroke [9].

In the present study, out of total study participants, mean serum GGT levels among cases was 56.84 ± 4.9 U/L and among controls it was 16.84 ± 3.2 U/L. This difference was statistically significant (p value < 0.05). Similar findings were reported in a study conducted by W yang et al among 880 patients of acute stroke and found significant association between serum GGT levels and occurrence of stroke. They reported high levels of GGT among patients of hemorrhagic and ischemic stroke [10].

In the present study, based on type of stroke, mean serum GGT levels among cases of hemorrhagic stroke was 59.5 ± 2.9 U/L and among cases of ischemic stroke it was 53.62 ± 5.2 U/L.

However, this difference was statistically not significant (p value > 0.05). Similar findings were

reported in a study conducted by M L Bots et al among patients of acute stroke and found significant association between serum GGT levels and occurrence of stroke. They reported high levels of GGT among patients of hemorrhagic and ischemic stroke [11].

Conclusion

We concluded from the present study that our study findings suggest that elevated serum gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) levels are significantly associated with an increased risk of stroke. This highlights the potential role of GGT as a biomarker for stroke risk assessment. However, further prospective studies are required to confirm the predictive value of GGT for stroke and to better understand its role in the development of cerebrovascular events.

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